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Methods for Studying Gender in Small-Scale Fisheries

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Abstract

Gender shapes the experiences and practices of communities that rely on small-scale fisheries (SSF) and gender relations are recognized as an important component of how households, economies, governance bodies, and societies operate. But how do scholars undertake research about gender and gender relations in the context of SSF? This working paper explores the wide variety of methods and methodologies used to study gender in SSF using an integrative literature review and a critical thematic synthesis. We outline the range of concepts and issues related to gender and SSF and review the various gender-focused and/or feminist methodologies and methods that may be appropriate for studying these issues. This working paper serves as an introduction to understanding the different kinds of gender issues that are studied in the context of SSF, perspectives on feminist methods, and suggestions for considering appropriate methods when designing gender-focused research.

Keywords Gender • Small-Scale Fisheries • Feminist Methodologies • Research Methods • Thematic Synthesis

1. Introduction

Gender inequality can undermine the lives and livelihoods of small-scale fishers. As observed by experts within the Vulnerability to Viability (V2V) Partnership, gender issues consistently emerge during research about social well-being, vulnerability, resource management, and fisheries governance (Galappaththi et al 2022, Galappaththi et al 2023, Kleiber et al 2015). Even when researchers are not actively planning to study gender-focused issues, gender-based differences in how people interact with their communities and operate within small-scale fisheries (SSF) may still emerge as important findings. These issues may range from gender relations within households, to gendered divisions of labour in fisheries' value chains, to the inclusion and exclusion of women from governance decisions across multiple levels of authority. Within all these issues, scholars point to gaps in our understanding about how gender shapes the experiences and practices of communities that rely on SSF (Kleiber et al 2015). Despite the strength in the gender and SSF literature, there is still much to learn about how gender and gender relations shape SSF and many ways to study these dynamics. In this paper, we review the important emerging scholarship on gender in SSF to summarize key methodological considerations and the range of methodological tools being used.

There are challenges that need to be considered in conceptualizing the role of gender relations in fisheries and in planning to study these social relations. The aim of this working paper is to provide a review of trends related to the study of gender issues in and around SSF. Our integrative literature review of 50+ papers on this topic produces two results: First, it gives us a sense of the wide range of concepts and issues related to gender and SSF that are relevant to scholars curious about these connections. These papers give

us a sense of the ontologies related to studying gender in SSF and may help other researchers to appropriately narrow the scope of which dimensions of gender-based research they may be interested in focusing on. By ontologies, we refer to the objects of study: what are the general categories of study when we examine this phenomenon.

Second, our review demonstrates the range of gender-focused and/or feminist methodologies and methods that may be appropriate for studying these various issues. This part of the paper is intended to be a useful guide to understanding different methodological approaches and the kinds of research tools that may be used to collect useful data on gender-focused issues. Moreover, this review also discusses the limitations of different approaches and important considerations for designing an effective study.

When undertaking gender-focused research, it is important to define key terms and pay attention to the uniqueness of local gender dynamics and norms. Overall, this working paper serves as an introduction to understanding some key terms, the different kinds of gender issues that are studied in the context of SSF, perspectives on feminist methods, and suggestions for considering appropriate methods when designing gender-focused research.

Box 1: Gender in SSF

Fisheries are often thought of as a masculine domain; however, research shows that women make significant contributions to the operations of SSF in both direct and indirect ways. Women comprise an estimated 40% of the SSF workforce, contributing to gleaning, fish processing and seaweed gathering (Galappaththi et al 2022). Yet women are frequently underrepresented in SSF decision-making, management, and governance and their contributions are sometimes “hidden” or overlooked by state officials and economists (Freeman and Svells 2022, Gustavsson and Riley 2018, Harper et al 2020, Pedroza-Gutiérrez and Hapke 2022, Tilley et al 2021). Moreover, gendered power relations can limit women’s ability to earn and control income, access or own resources, or have bodily autonomy, such as freedom of movement (Galappaththi et al 2022). While there has been recognition of the need for more gender equity in fisheries, it has been elusive in practice (Lawless et al 2021).

2. Methods

In this working paper, our objective is to explore the varieties of methods and methodologies used to study gender in SSF and to synthesize and categorize our findings. As such, we chose to undertake an integrative literature review and a critical thematic analysis (Ahmed et al 2025, Snyder 2015, Torraco 2005, Willig et al 2017). Integrative literature reviews are useful when exploring emerging research areas, as they synthesize findings from new areas of inquiry (Torraco 2005). Integrative reviews can yield several kinds of outputs, including establishing a research agenda and creating a taxonomy or categorization of concepts (Torraco 2005). Thematic analysis involves identifying themes within data, which can involve a range of rigid or flexible approaches (Willig et al 2017).

Our integrative literature review and thematic analysis (see. Fig. 1) is based on a collection of over 50 peer-reviewed journal articles published between 2015 and 2023 on gender issues within SSF. We select this period following the publication of the Voluntary Guidelines for Securing Sustainable Small-Scale Fisheries by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) in 2015 up until the initial point of data collection. The collection and initial review were conducted in early 2024 by the second author. Articles were specifically selected based on their focus on gender issues within SSF and gender

issues in a few adjacent resource sectors, such as small-scale agriculture. This is an emergent field and there is a relatively small number of studies that are specifically focused on gender and SSF. For this reason, an integrative review is appropriate to review some emerging trends in gender and SSF research and identify some common methods used to study these issues in similar sectors. Because our focus is on how to study gender and gender relations, we included a select number of studies from other sectors to compare and consider what other methodologies might be useful.

The second author (Carlos) reviewed the collected articles, drafted annotations for these articles, and identified several recurring themes, as well as noting the methods and methodologies of each paper. The first author (Collins) then coded each entry to identify major themes and trends. Two rounds of coding were undertaken: the first was to identify emerging themes and the kinds of methods and methodologies used by researchers; the second was to group and categorize topics. This more flexible approach to coding aligns with more creative approaches to thematic analysis, rather than technical approaches, and emerges from the researchers' interactions with the data (Willig et al 2017). Through this analysis, we identified two broad categories related to (1) thematic research concepts and issues, and (2) methods and methodologies. Within those two categories, we also identified several sub-categories. We will elaborate on those themes below.

Figure 1

Research Stages

Adapted from Torraco 2005, Willing et al 2017

To support the analysis of these sources, this paper also draws on feminist and gender-focused social science research both inside and outside of SSF for broader context. The first author used these texts to help synthesize the discussion of the major themes and develop a discussion of methodology in the context of

feminist analysis and gender studies. Together, these literatures provide important advice and considerations for those interested in conducting gender focused research.

3. Thematic findings

Our review revealed two major sub-categories of thematic concepts and issues related to gender. The first category includes the most common core concepts in SSF research where investigators are keen to apply gender analysis. As we discuss in the section below, these concepts include several known themes related to gender issues and SSF that have been identified in the literature and are also reflected in several scoping reviews (e.g. Galappaththi et al 2023). The second category, discussed in Section 3.2 below, captures several cross-cutting issues that are common to different kinds of research and areas of topical inquiry. These issue areas echo in similar lines of inquiry used in gender analysis beyond SSF, suggesting potential directions for further inquiry.

3.1 Core concepts: Gender, social well-being, and empowerment

Scholars interested in the study of gender, well-being and empowerment in SSF are joining an emerging field of study that draws upon decades of feminist research in different disciplines. Several studies pertaining to SSF and gender in our review focus on issues related to social well-being and empowerment, though they are often really focused on *women's* well-being and empowerment, despite often referring to gender. Given that issues of women's well-being and empowerment have often been overlooked in both policy and practice, there are good reasons to focus on matters of women's well-being and the extent to which women are "empowered". However, it is also important to clarify the meaning of key terms and explain the difference between studying gender and studying women and their experiences.

3.1.1 Gender

It is important to clarify that gender and women are not synonymous terms. The terms sex, gender, and intersectionality (among others) are used often in popular discussion, although sometimes used inaccurately. For example, many people in Western, English-speaking contexts conflate sex and gender as being one in the same. There are key differences between the definition of sex (a set of biological characteristics that include chromosomes, gene expression, hormone levels and function, and reproductive/sexual anatomy) and the definition of gender (socially constructed roles and expected behaviours that societies associate with one's sex). This distinction is important when we aim to research gender issues. Much of the research currently done in SSF pertains to gendered social relations and/or the roles that women play in SSF. However, certain biological differences between male, female, and intersex bodies may also be relevant: what happens to people when they become pregnant in SSF? What happens when someone needs to breastfeed? Do the work or social practices in SSF allow people to have their biological needs met in a safe way (e.g. dealing with menstruation in a socially acceptable manner)? Understanding the differences between sex and gender, and how they relate to each other, can offer us a more insightful picture into the nature of social relations in SSF.

It is also common for people to conflate the study of gender with just the study of women as a specific identity group. Because of historical gaps in research that often excluded the consideration of gender in a range of fields from history to evolutionary biology to medicine (Perez 2019), there are good reasons to try to close this gap by focusing on women as a group. Researchers often call for more gender- or sex-disaggregated data collection to better understand how women and gender minorities experience the world differently.

However, looking only at the experiences of women can also have some limitations. To just describe women's experiences without understanding the connection to social gendered expectations of women can miss the broader picture of why women have the experiences that they do. Understanding social gendered expectations also helps to consider how *men* also have experiences that are shaped by social gendered expectations. It is the expectations of both men and women that give us a broader understanding of structural gender issues and why societies are organized in particular ways. We will elaborate on this idea below.

Given this complexity, how can we study gender as a structural issue when we are accustomed to thinking about gender as part of individual identity? To deal with this, it is useful to think about gender in (at least) two ways:

- 1) as an individual's gender identity (e.g. someone who identifies as a woman, man, nonbinary, etc.), and
- 2) gender as a set of structural social relations that shapes how men and women, boys and girls, third gender, non-binary and gender non-conforming people are supposed to behave and interact. It includes societal expectations about how people are supposed to behave based on their biological characteristics.

These two distinctions show us how the social roles and expected behaviours associated with gender are often related and relational. Why is this useful? Studying women as a group is important, but if we do not also study the ideas about how women and men are expected to behave and interact, we lack the analysis needed to explain *why* women as a group have the experiences that they do. A structural or relational understanding of gender allows us to see the ways in which a particular society's expectations create the broader context within which gendered subjects (i.e. people!) operate in the world.

The other important piece here is that men should be considered gendered subjects too. Understanding gender as a social construct opens opportunities to consider men and masculinity, the expectations that societies put on men, the consequences of not conforming to those expectations, and so on. As we will see below, our exploratory review captures some intriguing observations about masculinity and resource governance. These observations offer important details about how governance occurs and who is considered the rightful decision-makers about key resources. Moreover, masculine expectations can shape all kinds of resource industries, including fisheries. There are genuine opportunities to explore the ways in which gender expectations affect men as well.

When designing research, the researcher should have a sense of what it is about gender that they want to study. Whether they are interested in the specific experiences of women in a particular part of a SSF value chain, the masculine norms of fishing practices, or the gender equity gaps within households, all are about gender in one way or another, but they focus on different aspects of social relations and may require different methodological tools for the design of the study (Weeratunge et al 2014).

3.1.2 Social wellbeing

Research on social wellbeing and empowerment typically draws from or refers to Amartya Sen's work on capabilities (e.g. Sen 2001) and/or Naila Kabeer's (1999) conceptualization of empowerment. Both scholars' contributions deepen understandings of poverty and wellbeing as multidimensional: that to understand people's experiences of poverty or insecurity means understanding more than just economic or material needs. Both Sen (2001) and Kabeer (1999) recognize that material needs are important but also highlight the importance of social context that limits people's capabilities and/or ability to make meaningful choices.

Biswal and Johnson's (2023) review of the gendered differences in social wellbeing is situated in the idea that social position will influence how one's experiences change in SSF. Their ethnographic study involved living within a the Koli fishing community in Saiyad Rajpara village, interviews, participant observation, informal discussions and field notes. Their analysis shows how there have been increases in people's material wellbeing due to the use of new technologies (e.g. employment, food security, economic opportunities), but that there are gendered differences in wellbeing. The shift from familial to commercial fisheries has improved some dimensions of women's lives: they are paid for work that used to be unpaid and have more autonomy as a result. This independence has even triggered a social backlash, with some families trying to arrange marriages for their daughters at an earlier age to prevent social embarrassment. In contrast, the commercial fishery has also resulted in a higher prioritization of economic relations rather than familial relations by young male fishers, which means more time spent fishing, higher levels of stress, and more alcohol consumption and gambling among male fishers. There have also been declining catch numbers, further increasing stress levels.

Studies like Biswal and Johnson's (2023) are helpful for showing the multidimensional quality of wellbeing and the importance of understanding gender as a relational concept. Here, it is not just examining men and women separately but understanding how the pressures on both men and women can also affect familial relations, marriage rates, male bonding, and so on. Importantly, they highlight how improvements in women's material wellbeing and independence can still trigger a social backlash, illustrating the pervasiveness in gender norms even in the context of material gains. They illustrate the ways in which material gains for women can challenge the status quo of gender relations and the ways in which the potential for greater independence for women can create social frictions.

Other scholars choose to focus specifically on women's wellbeing. Grantham, Lau and Kleiber (2020) study the multidimensional wellbeing of women gleaners in Timor-Leste. They note that gleaning – “the collection of marine organisms predominantly from the littoral zone” (Grantham, Lau and Kleiber 2020: 509) – is important for the food security of the rural poor and often a social activity for women. Like other activities peripheral to fisheries, gleaning is a topic that has not been widely examined, either by policymakers or scholarly research. They argue that the limited focus on gleaning as a subsistence activity taken on by women has the potential to reinforce essentialized narratives about women's inherent traits as caretakers. The authors justify their focus on the multidimensional wellbeing of women gleaners as important for generating new empirical research that goes beyond simplified, essentialist narratives. They used a mix of interviews, surveys and focus groups, including drawing and symbols, to learn about women's experiences in depth. This research enables the researchers to assess the various values of women gleaners, such as the valuing of gleaning as a social opportunity, enjoying nature and connections with their environment, seeking out favourite seafoods (rather than just meeting basic food security needs), and so on.

Grantham, Lau and Kleiber's (2020) choice to study the experiences and values of women gleaners is well-justified. They seek to overcome oversimplified narratives about women's caretaking and subsistence roles to illustrate how women have preferences and improve their wellbeing through this work. Their methodological approach is sensitive to women's capabilities, e.g. by using drawing to overcome the challenges of low literacy rates. Moreover, the work is more broadly situated in an understanding of social relations and the ways in which women may be excluded from governance and decision-making and the ways in which stereotypes (i.e. women are inherently caring and do subsistence work to care for others) can limit our understanding of social phenomena and gender roles.

As noted above, there is a tendency for some researchers to conflate gender with gender identity, specifically women as an identity group. But this study shows how focusing on women can fill important gaps in research, particularly where women's economic and social contributions have been understudied, undervalued, or where women's experiences have been generalized or essentialized. To study women's

specific experiences, it is useful to consider the broader structural gender relations as well, though it may not ultimately be the primary focus of the research.

At the same time, researchers can also expand their focus to think about gendered experiences as encompassing men, women, and those who do not fit the gender binary. Biswal and Johnson (2023) show us how understanding the different gendered impacts of commercial fisheries development has various impacts, both positive and negative on different dimensions of wellbeing and the impacts on marital and family relations. SSF scholars can thus expand the analysis to include a broader conception of gender to think about not just identity, but gender relations as well. This is a critical role that SSF researchers can play in correcting for the narrow ways that some researchers and policymakers have historically focused on women in limited or even stereotypical ways in fisheries and instead consider how gender is a broader relational concept that shapes how fisheries operate (Galappaththi et al 2022, Lawless et al 2021).

3.1.3 Empowerment

Several studies also focus on “empowerment,” though there is a lack of consistency in how the term is used. Our review identified several researchers who engage with Naila Kabeer’s (1999) multi-dimensional definition of empowerment. Kabeer’s concept of empowerment is often used by feminist scholars, researchers, and activists because it highlights different capacities – specifically, women’s access to resources and their agency – and individuals’ ability to realize that potential – specifically, their achievements. This multifaceted concept of empowerment captures the idea of someone being able to exercise agency to make meaningful choices in their life, rather than just getting access to resources. For instance, it goes beyond the idea that earning an income is inherently empowering, to consider whether a person gets to make meaningful, autonomous choices about how to spend that income or improve their wellbeing (Kabeer 1999). Conceptualized this way, empowerment is a process, rather than an endpoint. Empowerment is not something that can be given by an external actor but requires both resources and the opportunities to make meaningful decisions about one’s life (Kabeer 1999). It is thus context-specific and political, because it requires understanding different social norms, different kinds of power, and who can exercise power.

Even though many scholars engage with and cite Kabeer’s ideas, finding suitable indicators for “empowerment” can be a challenge. The papers in our review illustrate the kinds of choices researchers make in terms of empowerment indicators and the careful analysis that is needed. We summarize some of these different options in Table 1. For instance, Freeman and Svets (2022) use representation in Fisheries Local Action Groups (FLAGs) in Europe as an indicator of empowerment. However, their study reveals that although FLAGs have improved access to resources and improved agency for some women, there is limited evidence of women making meaningful choices. Torre et al (2019) also use Kabeer’s dimensions of resources, agency and achievements/outcomes to assess empowerment in fisheries in Mexico. However, they focus on achievements and outcomes in terms of whether women participate in fisheries management, are involved in government projects, or received support. While these are all important outcomes, the paper does not discuss whether these outcomes enabled women to make meaningful choices.

Table 1		
<i>Indicators of empowerment</i>		
Author(s)	Indicator(s) of Empowerment	Quantitative or Qualitative?
Freeman and Svets (2022)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Women’s representation in Fisheries Local Action Groups • Access to Resources 	Both

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agency and ability to make choices 	
Torre et al (2019)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Women’s participation in fisheries management • Women’s involvement in government projects • Received material supports 	Both
Gallardo-Fernández and Saunders (2018)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Structural approach to power relations 	Qualitative
Labayo (2023)	Using WEAI, focuses on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • decision-making, • resources, • income, • leadership, and time allocation 	Quantitative

In contrast, some scholars choose a more holistic or structural approach to the study of empowerment. Gallardo-Fernández and Saunders (2018: 180) use empowerment to understand the “active agency” of women in artisanal fisheries in Chile. They are attentive to different axes of power and the ways in which new women fishers clash against conventional expectations about women’s roles. While not the focal point of their study, these ideas show how a different definition of empowerment highlights the relational and structural qualities of gender analysis, rather than just material changes, participation, or inclusion. Their more expansive definition of empowerment that recognizes power relations offers additional layers of detail and empirical data and show the ways in which these women are exercising more autonomy in SSF.

There are also efforts to *quantify* empowerment, which requires choosing appropriate measurable indicators. The Women’s Empowerment in Agriculture Index (WEAI) and the Women’s Empowerment in Fisheries and Aquaculture Index (WEFI) are tools that try to quantify empowerment by assessing decision-making, resources, income, leadership, and time allocation. The tools capture multiple dimensions associated with empowerment in a broad sense without incorporating local specificities about how empowerment might be defined in communities. However, there are also critiques of such methodologies and questions about how much they overlook local contexts, which we explore in the sections below.

We identified studies that describe why the brief nature of these quantitative tools is advantageous for collecting gender-disaggregated data and developing quantitative datasets that attempt to evaluate different dimensions of empowerment. For instance, Labayo (2023) adapted the WEAI to apply to fishing communities in The Philippines and uses this measurable data to find that although women were more likely to have control of household income, they were not typically sole-decisionmakers or participants in fishing activities. Mengo et al (2023) find that despite higher participation in aquacultural seaweed farming, women still earn less than men. Moreover, they find that although women exercise more agency in terms of household decision-making, neither women’s increased participation in farm activities nor asset ownership is correlated with more decision-making over assets. Ragsdale et al (2022) use the WEFI to study gender equity among fishers, fish processors, and sellers in Zambia and show that although both men and women disagreed with patriarchal norms, in practice, men nonetheless still controlled key assets and decision-making. While the results of these studies often cannot offer detailed explanations of *why* we see these correlations without accompanying qualitative research, they do suggest important lines of inquiry based on quantitative findings.

For scholars interested in research on complex social concepts, it is important to specify your definitions and situate them within the broader debates around these terms. Some studies – like Macusi et al (2023) – use terms like “women empowerment” to describe government programs that were designed to assist women, but they do not engage with the broader literature on empowerment. Similarly, the term “empowerment” is often deployed by governments, NGOs, donors and international institutions without a clear definition. But feminist scholars have been critical of governments, policies, and scholarship that suggest empowerment is something that can be “given” to women, rather than it being a broader, multidimensional process involving social change and the exercise of strategic choices (Cornwall and Rivas 2015, Collins 2016, Addison et al 2021). Scholars that use empowerment as a concept to collect and/or analyze data also illustrate how there is often space for interpreting Kabeer’s ideas and a need for creative thinking about how to study it. But how scholars define these ideas and understand the sources of information about them will shape the methodological choices that they make.

3.2 Cross-cutting issues

In addition to these key concepts of gender, well-being, and empowerment, we also found that many of the studies in our review connected to dominant issues related to how gender is studied in and around resource industries and governance. There are compelling findings in our sample papers connected to the following topics:

Table 2	
<i>Cross-cutting issues</i>	
Theme	Definition
Exclusion of women from aspects of political, social and economic life	Findings that show how women are often unable to fully participate in aspects of public life, such as their absence from collective or communal decision-making and governance bodies. Alternately, where women are present in these spaces, their inability to speak up or participate on equal terms with men. Findings also show how women are excluded from certain economic activities, depending on the local context.
Lack of visibility of women’s contributions to economic and social wellbeing	The lack of recognition by communities of the contributions that women make to economies, such as through aspects of value chains that are less visible (e.g. drying fish, gleaning, etc.). Similarly, the lack of recognition of the unpaid care work often done by women that supports the wellbeing of their families and communities.
Lack of policy recognition of women’s economic contributions	When policy does not reflect the invisible labour of women, such as childcare, elder care, and other care work; informal labour; fish processing, drying, etc.
Gendered divisions of labour (e.g. in value chains; in households)	How societies assign tasks to people based on their presumed gender identity. This happens both

	within households according to societal assumptions and socialization of individuals, but also within the public sphere. For instance, where men are more likely to do the “masculine” work of fishing, and women are more likely to be involved in the processing of fish catches.
Gender biases and assumptions	<p>Gendered Assumptions: The beliefs that societies or individuals have about the appropriate or expected behaviours of people based on their gender identity.</p> <p>Gender Biases: discrimination against, or preferential treatment for, someone based on their gender identity.</p>
Gendered power relations	Unequal relations of power emerge because of gender-based divisions of labour, control over resources, acceptable behaviours or traits, and the socialization of people based on their sex (Ferguson 2021).
Taboos	“Taboos are unwritten laws based on societal values that are transmitted through socialisation; they help define who and how various groups and individuals in the community have access to fishing and fish,” (Oloko et al, 2023: 1)
Masculinity and femininity in social interactions	The study of masculinity and femininity both entail considering the social attributes associated with men and women, respectively, and the different configurations of these attributes in each social context (Salguero-Velázquez et al 2022).

It is beyond the scope of this review paper to fully investigate all these cross-cutting issue areas. However, we recommend that researchers investigating these kinds of gender issues seek out additional research on these topics beyond the scope of research on governance and SSF. Gender studies, development studies, feminist geography, sociology, anthropology, and political science are all fields and sub-fields in which researchers will be able to find useful concepts and advice for studying and researching these issues (see Agarwal 2000, Arora-Jonsson 2011, Arora-Jonsson 2014, Barrientos, Bianchi, and Berman 2019, Detraz 2016, Doss et al 2018, Elson 1991). Analytical perspectives like feminist political ecology and/or feminist political economy may be particularly helpful for making sense of the gender politics of resource industries like SSF (see Bakker 2007, Buechler and Hanson 2015, Razavi 2009, Rocheleau, Thomas-Slayter, and Wangari 1996, True 2012).

Below, we go a bit deeper on two key issue areas that we see strongly reflected in our review: the role of gender in shaping divisions of labour and value chains; and the role of gender in shaping participation in governance and resource management.

3.2.1 Gender, divisions of labour, and value chains

There are often distinct gendered divisions of labour in the practices of SSF (Kleiber et al 2015). This is reflected in our review, as most of the articles collected at least refer to gendered divisions of labour or different gender roles as an observed phenomenon in SSF. Within the fishing context, it is common to find that physical labour requiring more strength or exposure to danger – such as work involved in working long hours/days/weeks on fishing boats – is associated with masculine roles, while aspects of fish processing – gleaning, drying and the sale of raw or processed fish – is associated with feminine roles and can often be done closer to home. These productive roles associated with fishing activities may overlap with other reproductive roles, such as childcare, food gathering, or food preparation. Tasks that are less time-sensitive or can be done in the home or in a community space might be more likely to be done by women, enabling them to do multiple tasks at once (Pedroza-Gutiérrez and Hapke 2022, Roy 2023).

Scholars note that these roles played by women in SSF are overlooked and/or undervalued, whether by researchers, policymakers or even local members of communities (Galappaththi et al 2022). For these reasons, research on the gendered divisions of labour, and specifically, the roles women play in various SSF value chains, is important and is an emerging field of inquiry in the field. However, these roles are flexible and vary over time, and there are compelling exceptions to these norms that make for interesting scholarship (e.g. Saunders 2018). When used alongside the concept of gendered divisions of labour, analysts identify where women participate in the other practices that support or connect to fishing. Some scholars note that this type of analysis enables greater appreciation for the value added by women workers. Ideally, such research might influence policy and governance practices around fisheries to consider the various kinds of work that are done by women and other under-represented groups.

Some papers in our review also note the need to understand the gender roles and biases that shape gendered divisions of labour. When connected to the multi-faceted concept of empowerment described above, understanding these biases can help us to understand obstacles to equal pay and safe working conditions. Moreover, attention should also be paid to issues of workplace safety, sexual harassment, and assault when studying labour using a gender lens.

3.2.2 Participation, governance and resource management

In addition to women's participation in fisheries' economies and value chains, researchers are also interested in the extent to which women play a role in resource governance and management. Women's exclusion from governance processes is a global phenomenon, whether examining local resource governance or global modes of decision-making. While there are some exceptions, many communities that favour men in leadership, value masculine modes of leadership, and/or devalue feminine social behaviours often struggle to fully incorporate women into governance processes. For instance, if women are expected to not be argumentative or combative and docility is considered a feminine trait, women may not be comfortable participating in oppositional politics, when combative debate may be expected. Indeed, even when women do speak up, they may be ostracized or threatened by community or family members (Nunan and Cepić 2020). These are just some of the ways in which patriarchal social norms shape who participates and who is excluded from decision-making, even when there are not legal prohibitions.

It is thus for good reason that scholars of SSF have also focused on women's inclusion or exclusion from community-based resource governance and ownership of resources. A common critique of the concept of self-organized polycentric governance is that this concept tends to overlook the power dynamics that shape resource governance. While it is true that communities have often self-organized to manage resources, these practices have not always been undertaken equitably. Gender-focused and feminist research on SSF governance offers an important opportunity to deepen our understanding of power dynamics and exclusions in the management of fisheries and other resources.

Moreover, there are important findings even within our small sample of literature: for instance, one paper examining gender and governance finds that in cases where women have not been part of the development of conservation rules in fisheries, that women fishers will simply break those rules (Rohe et al 2018). This finding speaks to one of the core ideas in sustainability thought: that for sustainable practices to in fact be sustainable, they need to have community buy-in (Gibson et al 2013). Oloko et al (2024) delve into the role of taboos in the governance of SSF, and reveal the various ways in which religious, cultural and political expectations restrict women's participation in various ways.

4. Methodologies and methods

Given the social nature of the gender-related issues explored above, they can be empirically difficult to assess or measure. While experiences around gender inequality or gender difference are widespread, certain individual experiences may be difficult to capture in survey methods, especially where local practices and beliefs vary. Indeed, how best to capture social phenomena like these, particularly those that involve the experiences of people in different social positions, has long been a subject for debate among feminist scholars.

Before we discuss the various strategies and considerations for data collection or data production (Ramazanoglu with Holland 2002), we briefly discuss methodology from a theoretical perspective. It is useful to reflect on methodology, epistemology, and ontology and what these all mean for the purpose of selecting appropriate research methods. Below, we review the concept of methodology and the different types of methodological approaches that we saw in our exploratory literature review. Second, we review the different kinds of methods used that are consistent with these different methodological approaches. Due to the wide range of different methods and tools used in these studies, these tools will be grouped together as appropriate to discuss their advantages and disadvantages.

4.1 Methodologies

Methodologies refer to the theoretical framework(s) that guides the research and justifies the kinds of data that are needed and the tools best suited to collect them. Methodologies thus draw on understandings of epistemology, that is, how we know what we know, and ontology, the specific focal points of study.

Research on gender-based issues requires methodological choices about how we know what we know and assess what evidence is considered valid or not valid. These questions of epistemology are important. For example, if a researcher wants to understand peoples' gender-differentiated experiences of their social lives, we need to consider where that knowledge will come from and how do we know what is valid. Positivist methodologies expect highly controlled, value-neutral research design to produce measurable accounts of cause and effect, independent of the values of the researcher. Some critics note that such an approach overlooks the power that the researcher has in defining what is worthy of research and various tools they choose to conduct their work. Apart from that, this positivist understanding of the production of knowledge is often not applicable to understanding certain aspects of social phenomena, particularly those that seek to address the gaps that gender inequality has produced. For decades, feminist scholars have debated the appropriate methodologies for capturing the experiences of women that have historically been under-researched or understood. Debates about feminist standpoint epistemology – as one example – illustrate the debates among scholars about how to generate reliable data (Ramazanoglu with Holland 2002; Harding 1991; Haraway 1988). Ramazanoglu with Holland (2002: 138) suggest ten criteria we can use to assess the validity of knowledge, including:

- what forms of reason this knowledge claim depends on;

- whether this knowledge claim is confined to a local truth game or is more general;
- what evidence or other grounds exist for the claims made;
- what connections/disconnections are claimed between ideas, experiences and realities.
(Ramazanoglu with Holland 2002:138)

While this is not a list that all researchers “check off” while doing research, it does offer important insight into how researchers make decisions about their research and how they validate or triangulate the research that they conduct. Epistemological and methodological choices are implicit in the work that researchers do when they justify the collection of the data that they collect and why they interpret it to have the meaning that it does.

For example, in our review, case study methodologies are popular among scholars of SSF. Researchers using case studies develop in-depth analysis of a particular phenomenon in each place or context. It is premised on the idea that such deep understanding can offer us important insights about social dynamics. While they are often not widely generalizable, case study analysis may be able to develop “mid-range” theory about social phenomenon amongst certain populations or institutions, develop or challenge theory, or suggest new pathways for research (George and Bennett 2005).

Case study methodology is rooted in specific ideas about what different kinds of data can tell us, but there is still a wide range of diversity in how case studies might be developed. Case studies may or may not be comparative in nature. In the context of SSF, our review captured many different case study approaches that were rooted in specific fishing communities. Some of these studies examined several different communities in the same country or regional context to create a case study (e.g. Ferguson, 2021) while others compared fishing communities across countries but that shared similar features, like the presence of fisheries local action groups (Freeman and Svells 2022). It is beyond the scope of this paper to explain the variety of ways case studies may be useful, but there is a range of scholarship on how to design case studies that researchers can review.

In short, choosing a case study methodology supposes that a deep understanding of a specific case can offer us important insights about the world, in one form or another. It is rather different from a quantitative approach that seeks to gather population-level data that seeks generalizable conclusions.

4.1.1 A brief note on feminist methodology

There are debates among feminist scholars about whether there is such a thing as a “feminist methodology”. Indeed, feminist scholars use a wide range of different methodologies and understandings of knowledge to pursue research. For the purposes of this working paper, it is useful here to just offer a distinction between “feminist methodology” and approaches to gender-based research. Some scholars define feminist methodology or feminist research as being research that is connected to a broader goal of addressing gender-based inequality or injustice – of not just understanding the nature of inequality but also including an ethos that something should be done to address that inequality (Ramazanoglu with Holland 2002).

In contrast, gender-focused research need not have these same feminist goals or be considered “feminist” simply because it is focused on gender. Indeed, few of the papers that we identified in our review explicitly described feminist methodologies or even a feminist orientation. This may be for good reason. Feminist scholars are aware of the legacies of Western feminist research has that flattened and homogenized depictions of non-Western women (Mohanty 1988). Many feminist scholars from Western countries are now more careful to recognize power relations and privilege, and respect different cultural and social values. Many feminist scholars seek to design research that is oriented towards understanding gendered social relations and how they intersect with different social relations, such as class, race, ethnicity, and ability, but also the historical and contemporary patterns of colonialism.

We find several compelling examples of feminist research in fisheries that is more explicitly oriented to understanding gender differences in these contexts and the implications of such an understanding for equitable changes (e.g. Gerrard and Kleiber, 2019; Frangoudes, Gerrard and Kleiber 2019; Pedroza-Gutiérrez and Hapke 2022). It is up to the researcher to decide whether they approach their research with a feminist methodology or not. However, it is worth considering what knowledge is considered valid, why it is considered valid, and the proper focus (ontology) to generate or analyze the proper data. These are often also feminist questions.

4.2 Types of methods

4.2.1 *Quantitative analysis and methods*

If the methodological orientation of the researcher is to understand causal pathways to test hypotheses about which variables are relevant for causing a particular phenomenon (i.e. a positivist methodology), the researcher will likely want to be able to identify discrete variables and test the probability of their effect using statistical analysis. Such an approach requires quantitative methods that can collect population-level data to undertake numerical analyses. Given that gender equality is multifaceted, identifying linear causal pathways can be difficult. However, some tools like the Alkire-Foster Method (OPHI 2024), and the WEAI and WEF1 that are based on it, attempt to delineate some of the multiple dimensions that contribute to complex social concepts like poverty, wellbeing, vulnerability, and empowerment. While this approach has its limitations, it can indicate broader trends in a population, such as systemic lack of access to decision-making or resources. Choosing the right tools for data collection will be important for creating a reliable dataset.

The studies in our review that use these tools illustrate how a quantitative approach to empowerment can offer a straightforward approach to assessing the potential obstacles to gender equity in different contexts. The tool can be adapted for different levels of analysis and can generate the needed gender-disaggregated data in areas that have been historically understudied, like the gender dimensions in SSF. Moreover, the ability to disaggregate the multiple dimensions of empowerment also highlights how some positive outcomes on one dimension do not necessarily result in overall improvements in empowerment or wellbeing. All of these add important details to our understanding of the various dimensions of empowerment, even if the study itself does not focus on the exercise of meaningful choices. But there are limits to these approaches as well. The authors of these studies all point to the need to understand broader cultural norms and practices in greater depth and conclude with several suggestions for future research, including complementary qualitative research to better understand the findings.

There are critiques of analytical tools like the WEAI as well. Addison et al (2021) explore the ways in which tools like the WEAI move away from understandings of empowerment that emphasize power relations. They explain that context is critical for understanding local practices, such as overlapping ownership claims on assets. Questions that distinguished between individual purchases and household purchases created confusion for some respondents, as the distinction did not fit with family-level practices and couldn't account for extended family households or polygynous (i.e. one husband and multiple wives) households (Addison et al 2021). They conclude that “[t]he A-WEAI relies on categories and codes that produce distorted representations of intrahousehold dynamics,” largely because of the individualistic assumptions embedded within (Addison et al 2021: 286). More broadly, they express skepticism that quantitative surveys with brief qualitative components attached will not offer a sufficiently nuanced perspective on the various barriers to meaningful empowerment if they are done too quickly.

Household surveys beyond the WEAI or Alkire-Foster method may also be prone to these problems. Household-level surveys are a popular research tool, however, when trying to capture information about

gendered division of household tasks or household relationships, a survey completed by a male head of household or in the presence of a spouse or other family members might not capture the full scope of the problems. This can create bias in the responses, especially if there is not awareness of how different household members perceive the situation. And even if multiple members of a household are surveyed, a lack of privacy might also not result in a complete picture of household relations. For these reasons, certain modes of data collection may not be appropriate or have significant limitations that need to be accounted for. It is critical that researchers be aware of these limits and try to mitigate them as possible.

Table 3	
<i>Examples of quantitative data collection methods and tools</i>	
Quantitative Tool	Description
Alkire-Foster (AF) Method <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Women's Empowerment in Agriculture Index (WEAI) • Women's Empowerment in Fisheries and Aquaculture Index (WEFI) 	The AF Method is an approach designed to quantify various aspects of multidimensional concepts like poverty, wellbeing, happiness, etc. (OPHI 2024). The method involves identifying several indicators to match different dimensions and the use of surveys (individual or household) to collect and analyze data. Research indices like WEAI and WEFI use this approach in the study of fisheries.
(Fish) Catch Data Analysis	Fish catch data is typically collected at the national scale, focusing on large-scale commercial fishers. Harper et al (2020) analyze this data in combination with rates of women's participation in fisheries to estimate women's levels of activity at one point in the value chain.
Household Surveys	Systematic collection of data using a standardized set of questions where one member of the household usually responds on behalf of the entire household.
Individual Surveys and Questionnaires	Systematic collection of data using a standardized set of questions with an identified population. May also be referred to as a structured interview.
Statistical Analysis using Activities Diary	Tilley et al (2021) created a fishing activities diary and a form for gleaning activities for women across 9 communities in Timor-Leste. Women were asked to record their daily fishing activities and income, including the date, the method, and if the catch was sold/consumed. Data from each tool each were analyzed using statistical methods to assess the relative importance of species in gleaning, assess differences in income based on species, location, activity, etc.

4.2.2 Qualitative analysis and methods

Qualitative methodology and methods are well-equipped to get into the complex social dynamics that shape well-being, divisions of labour, governance, gender roles and so on. Quantitative methodology and methods discussed above are more often used to capture information about broader populations and groups and can help to generate new research questions and puzzles. However, qualitative research often helps researchers to develop more thick descriptions of social phenomenon, to probe the meaning of ideas or investigate individual experiences in greater depth. We list several common tools below, but we find that interviews with various populations, focus group discussions, and field/participant observation are commonly used by qualitative researchers in SSF. These may or may not be paired with surveys, questionnaires, or quantitative data.

In some cases, qualitative research may have the expressed purpose of trying to improve the experiences of participants, such as Participatory Action Research (PAR). Such research is premised on doing research that is not just about a community but actively involves communities in research design that is socially and culturally appropriate and is oriented towards helping communities reach their own goals. Such research must be done in close consultation with communities and can be time-consuming when done appropriately. We identified a couple of studies that used forms of participatory data collection in their work or surveyed existing research on participatory monitoring (Gallardo-Fernández and Saunders 2018, House et al 2022). Gallardo-Fernández and Saunders (2018) used participatory data collection to have participants brainstorm about their experiences and map territorial use rights. House et al (2022) note that despite the usefulness of participatory monitoring to close gaps and data collection and empower community members that very few cases combine gender and participatory monitoring, suggesting an opportunity for more research to be done.

Challenges exist with qualitative methods. While social issues like gender inequality can be captured and described well using qualitative tools, there are also challenges in collecting accurate data that is sensitive to local cultural contexts and values. For instance, there can be challenges about asking questions about inequality in instances where gender inequality is not perceived to be a problem. Many people in a community – regardless of their gender identity – may view gender roles, assumptions, divisions of labour, etc. as normal or natural and not worth discussing. Moreover, such roles, ideas, and divisions of labour may or may not be the source of hardship for members of a community. It is important that qualitative tools including survey, focus group, and interview questions be designed (and revised) to be sensitive to local practices and beliefs. There is the added challenge of trying to probe about gender issues in culturally appropriate ways and, depending on the nature or goal of the research, to attempt to discover the sources of gender differences in SSF.

These raise important ethical and practical research design issues that all researchers need to be aware of. It is critical to consider what risks there may be for marginalized populations to speak with researchers or participate in activities. Many researchers opt to employ same-sex focus group discussions to enable people to speak more freely in contexts where patriarchal norms might inhibit women. Researchers must also recognize their own positionality in the conduct of research, and the power they may unknowingly exercise over research participants. In the end, no research design is perfect, but considering the limitations of certain methods is imperative for a successful research project and the ethical conduct of research.

Table 4	
<i>Examples of qualitative data collection methods and tools</i>	
Qualitative Tool	Description
Drawing Activities	Participants are asked to make illustrations, prompted by the researcher/facilitator. These may be done alone or in focus groups (see below).

	<p>Grantham, Lau and Kleiber (2020) use drawing and symbol-based activities to be more inclusive of populations with lower literacy rates.</p>
Field Observation or Participant Observation	<p>The researcher makes field notes based on observations of public behaviours or events where they are permitted to attend and observe (e.g. Gerrard and Kleiber 2019). Field notes are written by the researcher and include both descriptive data as well as reflections on what they observe.</p>
<p>Focus Group Discussions (FGDs)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mixed-gender focus group • Single-gender focus group 	<p>Participants interact with other participants, responding to questions from the researcher(s) and/or facilitator(s). FGDs may prompt participants to respond in different ways than they might have if interviewed alone (e.g. Grantham, Lau and Kleiber 2020).</p> <p>Feminist and gender-focused researchers have noted that there is a need to reflect on whether FGDs have single- or mixed-gender groups. Researchers note that women may be more open to speaking in single-gender groups than in mixed-gender groups. This can be due to social context, the nature of questions asked, or other factors. However, there can be good reasons to have mixed-gender groups as well, such as seeing how they interact or respond to prompts similarly or differently.</p>
<p>Interviews, semi-structured</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exploratory • Key informant • Expert • Community members 	<p>Using an interview guide, researchers ask questions of participants to investigate broader research questions. Semi-structured interviews have a pre-determined list of questions but allow for diversions from the list to explore key themes related to the research. This differs from surveys and questionnaires that are more structured</p> <p>Exploratory interviews may be used in the early stages of a project to understand the research context or challenges from the perspective of participants. Key informants are people with first-hand knowledge or expertise about an issue or context. Experts are those with specialized or in-depth knowledge, such as researchers or traditional knowledge-keepers. Finally, community members can answer questions about their experiences and context.</p>

Literature Review	Systematic or scoping reviews of existing academic literature have been used to synthesize key research findings and understand the state of the field (e.g, Galappaththi et al 2022, House et al 2022, Oloko et al 2024).
Participatory Data Collection	Methods that include participants in a meaningful way, usually with the objective of increasing participant capacities, skills, or awareness about their conditions. May also involve adapting data collection strategies in consultation with participants. Often linked to the work of Paulo Friere (2018).
Resource use mapping	A participatory method wherein participants identify who has access to and control of key resources. Can be useful to identify gender differences in access and control of resources (e.g. Torell et al 2021).
Time allocation/Time mapping	Participatory method that has participants describe how they use their time throughout the day. Can be useful to identify gender differences in how people use their time (e.g. Torell et al 2021).

5. Conclusions

There is tremendous opportunity for scholars to expand our understanding of SSF via closer attention to various aspects of gender identity and relations. As outlined above, this is still an emerging area of study, but there is a wealth of scholarship that can help researchers understand the various dimensions of gender relations that are relevant to the study of fisheries communities and resource industries. We encourage researchers to think carefully about the aspects of gender relations they are interested in and design their research approach accordingly. There is a range of research engaging with key concepts and themes with which scholars can engage to define core ideas and build upon. Not all research tools can capture the nuance of local biases and expectations, nor should we expect localized study to produce generalizable conclusions. And yet, both kinds of tools are useful and relevant to better understanding the world in which we live. Scholarship on gender and SSF is critical for us to better understand the connections between livelihoods and well-being in this sector.

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Vulnerability to Viability (V2V) Global Partnership

The Vulnerability to Viability (V2V) project is a transdisciplinary global partnership and knowledge network. Our aim is to support the transition of small-scale fisheries (SSF) from vulnerability to viability in Africa and Asia. Vulnerability is understood as a function of exposure, sensitivity and the capacity to respond to diverse drivers of change. We use the term viability not just in its economic sense but also to include its social, political, and ecological dimensions.

The V2V partnership brings together approximately 150 people and 70 organizations across six countries in Asia (Bangladesh, India, Indonesia, Japan, Malaysia, Thailand), six countries in Africa (Ghana, Malawi, Nigeria, Senegal, South Africa, Tanzania), Canada and globally. This unique initiative is characterized by diverse cultural and disciplinary perspectives, extensive capacity building and graduate student training activities, and grounded case studies from two regions of the world to show how and when SSF communities can proactively respond to challenges and creatively engage in solutions that build their viability. Further information on the V2V Partnership is available here: www.v2vglobalpartnership.org.

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